

A Comparative Study between Early Vs Late Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy in Patients with Choledocholithiasis after ERCP

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Abstract:

Introduction: Choledocholithiasis, the presence of stones in the common bile duct, can be primary or secondary, with secondary being more common. Diagnosis typically involves symptoms and imaging, with ERCP serving as both diagnostic and therapeutic. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is the gold standard treatment, and studies indicate better outcomes when performed within 72 hours post-ERCP. This study aims to evaluate optimal timing for laparoscopic cholecystectomy after ERCP and assess associated morbidity.

Methodology: This prospective randomized study at JLN Medical College between December 2022 to July 2024 evaluated 50 patients with concomitant gallbladder and CBD stones, divided into early (within 3 days) and late (4 weeks after ERCP) laparoscopic cholecystectomy groups. Data collected included demographics, pre-operative findings, and intraoperative outcomes to assess surgical efficacy and complications and also post-operative morbidity and hospital stay

Results: The study includes 50 patients with concomitant gallbladder and CBD stones, which are randomly arranged in two groups i.e. early and late laparoscopic cholecystectomy after ERCP with mean age of patients was 48.10 years, predominantly female (72%). Abdominal pain was reported in 90% of cases. Early cholecystectomy resulted in significantly shorter operation times (37.6 vs. 54.2 minutes) and reduced hospital stays (29.92 vs. 62.48 hours). Additionally, this group had fewer intraoperative complications, highlighting the benefits of early intervention.

Conclusion: The study recommends early cholecystectomy for patients with cholelithiasis and choledocholithiasis post-ERCP, citing benefits like shorter procedure times, fewer complications, less postoperative pain, and reduced hospital stays. These findings support timely intervention, though further research with larger sample sizes is needed for definitive guidelines on surgical timing.

Keywords: Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy, Choledocholithiasis, ERCP.

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Introduction

Choledocholithiasis is the presence of stones within common bile duct. These secondary bile stones are cholesterol stones in 75% and black pigment stones in 25% of patients. Primary bile duct stones originate from within the bile ducts and are more commonly seen in Asian populations. These stones are correlated with biliary stasis and bacteria.[1] The diagnosis of choledocholithiasis is initially by symptomatology, laboratory tests, and ultrasound findings. Abdominal ultrasound being the most commonly used initial diagnostic tool for suspected biliary stones has a sensitivity of 25-60% and spec-

ificity of 95-100%.[2] Incidence of CBD stones in cases of cholelithiasis is around 3.4%-15%.[3] With the introduction of Endoscopic sphincterotomy, ERCP is now developed as a therapeutic tool with sensitivity of 90% and specificity of 98%.[4] ERCP stone extraction is successful 80% - 90% of the time using the techniques of sphincterotomy and balloon catheter or Dormia basket stone retrieval.[5] Pancreatitis is the most common complication seen after ERCP.[6] Long term complications include papillary stenosis, cholangitis and recurrent choledocholithiasis.[7] Laparoscopic

cholecystectomy is considered gold standard for treatment of symptomatic cholelithiasis.[8] In a patient with concomitant cholelithiasis with choledocholithiasis, according to recent studies, the overall outcome is better if Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy is performed early (<72 hours).[9] There was a significant rate of conversion to open cholecystectomy in cases performed after 6 weeks, than within the first week after ERCP.[10] This study is to understand the management of CBD stones with importance to the optimal timing required for laparoscopic cholecystectomy after an ERCP procedure at this institute. It aims to find out the intra and post-operative morbidity in early laparoscopic cholecystectomy after ERCP and its benefits over a late laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Aims and Objectives: To compare the clinical outcome, intra-operative complications between early and late laparoscopic cholecystectomy in cases of choledocholithiasis who underwent ERCP stone retrieval in terms of (i) Duration of surgery (ii) Degree of adhesions (iii) Post-operative morbidity (iv) Hospital stay.

Material and Methods: A prospective randomised study conducted on patients who presented with concomitant Gall bladder and common bile duct stones to be managed at JLN Medical College & Hospital, Ajmer during a period from December 2022 to July 2024.

Group I (n=25): Early LC performed within 3 days after ERCP

Group II (n=25): Late LC performed 4 weeks after ERCP

Inclusion Criteria: Patients aged between 15 and 80 years presenting with concomitant CBD and GB stones

Exclusion Criteria: Patient unfit for surgery, Patients with persistent cholangitis, Patients with

post ERCP complications, Patients with persistent CBD stone after ERCP, Patients unwilling to enroll for study

Patients' age, gender, preoperative workup data, including laboratory investigations (white blood cells, serum amylase, liver enzymes serum bilirubin) and, ERCP (size of the stones, number of stones, number of attempts, procedure duration), imaging investigations (magnetic resonance cholangio-pancreaticography, ultrasound) of the GB and bile ducts and timing of LC after ERCP (early or late) were recorded.

Liver condition, loss of blood, conversion rate, duration of surgery, technical challenges, GB perforation, bile duct injuries, GB appearance, GB material, GB stones (number and size) were noted.

The severity of adhesion was scored as per the following grading scale as suggested by Ercan et al. [11] Adhesions of a certain nature (1-no adhesions, 2-mild adhesions, 3-severe adhesions encasing gall bladder, 4-severe adhesions involving other organs). A combination of clinical criteria [biliary colic, jaundice, cholangitis, and pancreatitis] and ultrasonography, MRCP and necessary investigations was used to diagnose choledocholithiasis.

Statistical Analysis

Data Entry was done using Microsoft excel 2013 and analysis done using SPSS V 16. Qualitative data was expressed in frequencies and percentages and Quantitative data in mean and standard deviation. Unpaired t test was used for parametric data. Bar diagrams and pie chart were used to represent the data. P value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Age and Gender distribution

Age distribution (Years)	Early Cholecystectomy		Late Cholecystectomy		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
21 – 30	2	8%	2	8%	4	8%
31 – 40	3	12%	9	36%	12	24%
41 – 50	6	24%	6	24%	12	24%
51 – 60	10	40%	5	20%	15	30%
61 – 70	2	8%	3	12%	5	10%
71 – 80	2	8%	0	0%	2	4%
Total	25	100%	25	100%	50	100%
Mean ± SD	50.72 ± 12.47		45.48±12.39		48.01 ± 12.59	
Chi square test= 6.86, p=0.23, Not statistically significant						
Gender distribution	Early Cholecystectomy		Late Cholecystectomy		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Male	4	16%	10	40%	14	28%
Female	21	84%	15	60%	36	72%
Total	25	100%	25	100%	50	100%
Chi square test= 3.50, p=0.06, Not statistically significant						

Table 2: Clinical, Radiological and Intraoperative findings

	Early Cholecystectomy		Late Cholecystectomy		Total		
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Clinical findings							
Murphy's sign	2	8%	5	20%	7	14%	
Tenderness Right Hypochondrium	10	40%	6	24%	16	32%	
Palpable lump	3	12%	1	4%	4	8%	
USG Findings							
GB wall thickness	<5 mm	22	88%	15	60%	37	74%
	>5 mm	3	12%	10	40%	13	26%
CBD diameter	<10 mm	8	32%	15	60%	23	46%
	>10 mm	17	68%	10	40%	27	54%
Intraoperative Gall bladder findings							
Bile	23	92%	21	84%	44	88%	
Mucocele	2	8%	4	16%	6	12%	
Pyocele	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	
Total	25	100%	25	100%	50	100%	

Table 3: Size of CBD stones

Size of CBD stones	Early Cholecystectomy		Late Cholecystectomy		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
<5 mm	8	32%	9	36%	17	34%
5 – 15 mm	11	44%	12	48%	23	46%
>15 mm	6	24%	4	16%	10	20%
Total	25	100%	25	100%	50	100%

Table 4: Grades of pericholecystic adhesions

Grade	Early Cholecystectomy		Late Cholecystectomy		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
I	2	8%	5	20%	7	14%
II	12	48%	10	40%	22	44%
III	11	44%	8	32%	19	38%
IV	0	0%	2	8%	2	4%
Total	25	100%	25	100%	50	100%

Table 5: Mean Values

Mean	Early Cholecystectomy	Late Cholecystectomy
Duration of surgery (Mins)	37.60 ± 9.47	54.20 ± 18.35
P value	0.0002*	
Post-operative mean values		
WBC count	6.8 + 1.00	5.1 + 0.50
Serum Bilirubin	1.36 + 0.23	1.01 + 0.17
Drain output on post-operative Day 1	18 ml + 2.3	27 ml + 1.95

Table 6: Mean Duration of Hospital stay after surgery

Mean Duration of Hospital Stay	Early Cholecystectomy	Late Cholecystectomy	P value
Duration of Hospital stay in hours	29.92 ± 15.69	62.48 ± 29.85	0.01*

Table 7: Conversion

Conversion	Early Cholecystectomy		Late Cholecystectomy	
	N	%	n	%
Yes	0	0	0	0
No	25	100%	25	100%
Total	25	100%	25	100%

Discussion

In the present study, the mean age for early cholecystectomy was 50.72 years, and for late cholecystectomy, it was 45.48 years. This compares to a study by El Nakeeb A et al. (2016)¹¹ where the

mean age for early cholecystectomy was 43 years and for late cholecystectomy, it was 47 years. Similarly Gupta et al[12] (2022) found a mean age of 44.60±14.96 years for the early group and 46.37±9.23 years for the delayed group. Similarly,

Chandrakala et al[13] reported mean ages of 41.5 years in the early group and 38.6 years in the delayed group. Mohsin et al[14] (2023), reported a mean age of 42.2 ± 12.25 years in the Early Cholecystectomy group and 42.18 ± 12.43 years in the Delayed Cholecystectomy group. Similarly, the study by Neetha et al[15] (2023) observed a mean age of 40.16 ± 10.14 years for the Early Cholecystectomy group and 36.92 ± 8.49 years for the Late Cholecystectomy group. These findings support the observation that younger patients tend to undergo early surgery, while older patients are more likely to face delayed interventions. In the present study, 84% of patients undergoing early cholecystectomy were female, compared to 60% in the late group. This trend is reflected in the study by El Nakeeb A et al. (2016) [11] where there were 71% females in early cholecystectomy and 65% females in late cholecystectomy. Sharma A et al[16] where females represented 67.06% of immediate surgeries and 54.62% of delayed cases. Likewise, Ghoneim et al[17] found that females accounted for 81% of early interventions. Both studies highlight the higher likelihood of females undergoing early cholecystectomy compared to males. Gupta et al[12]. (2022) similarly reported a female predominance, with 73.3% females in the early group and 53.3% in the delayed group. Chandrakala et al[13] also observed a higher proportion of females in both groups, with 85% in the early group and 75% in the delayed group. This consistent female preponderance across multiple studies reflects the higher incidence of gallstone disease in women, often attributed to hormonal factors. (Table 1)

The present study showed tenderness in the right hypochondrium in 40% of early cases and 24% of late cases, while Murphy's sign was positive in 8% of early and 20% of late cases. In comparison, Ghoneim et al[17] reported that Murphy's sign was a significant finding in 10% of cases, and right upper quadrant tenderness was noted in 32% of early cholecystectomy patients. In Gupta et al[12]. (2022), Murphy's sign was positive in 86.7% of early cases and 20% of late cases, showing a similar trend. This consistency suggests that tenderness and Murphy's sign are crucial clinical indicators, with higher positivity rates in early surgical interventions. Moshin et al[14] (2023) reported similar findings, where tenderness was a significant clinical sign in their study population. Similarly, Neetha et al[15] (2023) found that the incidence of clinical signs such as fever and right upper quadrant tenderness was comparable between early and late groups. These clinical findings consistently highlight tenderness as a critical indicator of gallbladder pathology. In the present study, 88% of patients in the Early Cholecystectomy group had a gallbladder wall thickness of less than 5 mm, compared to 60% in the Late Cholecystectomy group. In contrast, in the study by El Nakeeb A et al. (2016)[11] 80% of

the patients in early cholecystectomy group had a gallbladder wall thickness of less than 5 mm, compared to 89% in the Late Cholecystectomy group. Sharma A et al [16] reported that 75% of patients with late laparoscopic cholecystectomy showed increased gallbladder wall thickness. Another study by Ghoneim et al[17] found that 68% of patients with delayed surgery had a thickened gallbladder wall, consistent with the findings of the present study. In a study by Moshin et al[14] (2023), gallbladder wall thickening was reported in 76% of early surgery cases and 84% of delayed surgery cases. Similarly, Neetha et al[15] (2023) reported gallbladder wall thickening in 76% of both Early and Late Cholecystectomy groups, showing that thickening is a common finding, particularly in delayed interventions. Gupta et al[12] (2022) reported that 33.3% of early cholecystectomy patients had a thickened gallbladder wall, compared to 6.7% in the delayed group. Similarly, Chandrakala et al[13] (2022) noted that 60% of early patients had thickened gallbladders. These findings confirm that delayed interventions are often associated with more severe inflammation. In the present study, 92% of Early Cholecystectomy patients had bile present in the gallbladder, and 8% had a mucocele 84% of late cholecystectomy patients had bile present in the gall bladder and 16% in mucocele. Similarly, in the study of El Nakeeb A et al. (2016)[11] 84% of the early cholecystectomy patients and 92% of the late cholecystectomy patients had bile in the gall bladder. Ghoneim et al[17] reported that 90% of early surgery patients presented with bile, while 10% had a mucocele. Moshin et al[14] (2023) reported that mucocele formation was more common in delayed surgeries due to bile stasis. Similarly, Neetha et al[15] (2023) found that bile retention was a typical finding in early surgery, while more severe complications like mucocele were found in delayed surgeries. Current study finding aligns with the study by Gupta et al[12] (2022), where a higher proportion of patients in delayed surgeries had mucocele formation due to prolonged bile stasis. Chandrakala et al[13] (2022) also found a higher rate of mucocele in delayed cholecystectomy patients, confirming that prolonged inflammation often leads to the development of mucoceles in delayed surgeries. (Table 2)

In the present study, the most common size of CBD stones was between 5-15 mm, found in 44% of Early Cholecystectomy patients and 48% of Late Cholecystectomy patients. In the study of El Nakeeb A et al. (2016)[11] the most common size of CBD stone was <5 mm found in 65% of early cholecystectomy patients and 54% of late cholecystectomy patients. Sharma A et al[16] reported a similar distribution, with 42% of early surgery patients and 46% of late surgery patients having stones of 5-15 mm. In comparison, Moshin et al[14] (2023) reported a slightly higher incidence

of stones larger than 10 mm in the delayed group. Gupta et al[12] (2022) reported similar findings, with 46% of early surgery patients and 52% of late surgery patients having stones between 5–15 mm. Likewise, Chandrakala et al[13]. Found that most stones fell in this size range in both early and delayed surgeries. These consistent results indicate that stone size is relatively comparable between early and late surgeries, but larger stones tend to be more prevalent in delayed cases. (Table 3)

The present study revealed that 48% of Early Cholecystectomy patients had Grade II adhesions, compared to 40% in the Late Cholecystectomy group. Similarly in the study of El Nakeeb A et al. (2016)[11] 40% of the early cholecystectomy patients had Grade II adhesions compared to 42% in the late cholecystectomy group. In contrast, Sharma A et al[16] found that 58% of patients undergoing late surgery had Grade III or higher adhesions. Ghoneim et al[17] also noted that late cholecystectomy was associated with a higher incidence of severe adhesions, reflecting the increased difficulty of the procedure as the inflammation progresses. Moshin et al[14] (2023) found that adhesions were more common in delayed surgeries, with 36% of late surgery patients presenting with severe adhesions compared to 12% in the early group. Neetha et al[15] (2023) also reported that adhesions were more frequent in delayed cases, reflecting the chronic inflammation associated with prolonged disease. Gupta et al[12] (2022), where more severe adhesions (Grade III and IV) were predominantly observed in delayed cholecystectomy cases. Chandrakala et al[13] also reported higher rates of severe adhesions in patients undergoing delayed surgery, likely due to the increased inflammatory response over time. (Table 4)

The mean duration of surgery in the present study was significantly shorter for Early Cholecystectomy (37.6 minutes) compared to Late Cholecystectomy (54.2 minutes). In the study conducted by El Nakeeb A et al. (2016)[11] the mean operative time was 50 minutes for early cholecystectomy group and 60 minutes for late cholecystectomy group. Sharma A et al[16] reported a similar trend, with early surgeries taking 40 minutes on average and late surgeries extending to 60 minutes. Ghoneim et al[17] also found that delayed procedures were associated with a significantly longer operative time due to increased adhesions and technical difficulty. Moshin et al[14]. (2023) similarly reported longer operative times for delayed surgeries, with a mean of 60.72 minutes in the delayed group and 83.55 minutes in the early group. Neetha et al[15] (2023) found that early surgery had shorter operative times as well, with a mean duration of 45.6 minutes for early procedures compared to 65.2 minutes for delayed surgeries. In comparison, Gupta et al[12]. (2022) found the mean operative

time to be 65.78 minutes in the early group and 56.83 minutes in the delayed group. Another study by Saber et al[18] (2021) reported a mean duration of 104.3 minutes in the early group and 93 minutes in the delayed group. The longer durations observed in other studies may be attributed to more complex cases or different surgical settings. In the present study, the mean WBC count was 6.8 in the Early Cholecystectomy group and 5.1 in the late group. The study by Sharma A et al[16] found that early surgery patients had a mean WBC count of 7.2, while late surgery patients had a count of 5.5. These findings suggest that early surgery is associated with a higher inflammatory response, as indicated by elevated WBC counts. The study by Moshin et al[14] (2023) also reported higher inflammatory markers in early surgery patients, reflecting acute inflammatory states. Neetha et al[15] (2023) found that biochemical markers such as bilirubin and ALP were elevated in early surgery patients due to the more acute phase of the disease. The serum bilirubin level was also higher in the early group (1.36) compared to the late group (1.01). Similar trends were observed in the study by El Nakeeb A et al. (2016)[11] where the serum bilirubin level was 1.5 in early cholecystectomy group compared to 1.2 in late cholecystectomy group. Chandrakala et al[13] (2022) where early surgeries showed elevated WBC counts and liver enzymes. These elevated values in early surgeries reflect the acute inflammatory state, which is expected to decrease after delayed surgery as inflammation subsides. (Table 5)

In the present study, the mean hospital stay was significantly shorter for Early Cholecystectomy patients (29.92 hours) compared to Late Cholecystectomy patients (62.48 hours). This is consistent with the findings of Sharma A et al[16] who reported that early surgery patients had a mean hospital stay of 3 days, while late surgery patients had an average stay of 6 days. Ghoneim et al[17] also found a similar pattern, with shorter hospital stays associated with early interventions. Moshin et al[14] (2023) who reported a shorter mean hospital stay of 1.98 days in the early group versus 3.35 days in the delayed group. Similarly, Neetha et al[15] (2023) reported shorter stays for early surgery patients (2.4 days) compared to delayed surgery patients (5.6 days).

Gupta et al[12]. (2022), study reported a shorter hospital stay in the early group (3.40 days) compared to the delayed group (6.27 days). Saber et al[18]. (2021) also found that early surgery significantly reduced hospital stay, with an average of 4.8 days for early surgery and 9.2 days for delayed surgery. These findings highlight the economic and patient recovery benefits of early intervention. (Table 6) In the present study, no conversions to open surgery were recorded in either group. In contrast

to El Nakeeb A et al. (2016)¹¹ the percentage of conversion was 9% in early cholecystectomy group and 11% in late cholecystectomy group. Similarly, both Sharma A et al^[16] and Ghoneim et al^[17] reported low conversion rates in their studies, with early surgeries showing a conversion rate of less than 1%. Moshin et al^[15] (2023), who reported a low conversion rate, with 5.3% in the Early Cholecystectomy group and 8.0% in the delayed group. Neetha et al^[15]. (2023) reported higher rates of conversion in delayed surgeries, with 32% of delayed cases converted to open surgery compared to 20% of early surgeries. Similarly, Gupta et al^[12] (2022) found that conversion rates were low, with 6.7% of early cholecystectomy patients and none in the delayed group requiring conversion. Saber et al^[18] (2021) reported a slightly higher conversion rate of 15% in early surgeries, but noted that delayed cases had an even higher conversion rate of 20%. These results demonstrate that early laparoscopic cholecystectomy can be safely performed with a low risk of conversion to open surgery.

Conclusion

The study concludes that early cholecystectomy is preferable for patients with cholelithiasis and choledocholithiasis after ERCP offering several advantages over late cholecystectomy. Early surgery is associated with a shorter duration of the procedure, fewer intraoperative complications, reduced postoperative pain, and a significantly shorter hospital stay. These findings suggest that early intervention can improve patient outcomes and reduce the overall burden of hospital resources. The results emphasize the need for a timely surgical approach in managing gallbladder-related conditions to minimize complications and enhance recovery. Considering the smaller sample size it is recommended that further randomization studies with larger sample size are required for a definitive decision for the time of laparoscopic cholecystectomy after an ERCP.

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